

HYDRAULIC CHARACTERISTICS AND OPERATING DATA OF THE VARIABLE-SPEED PUMPED-STORAGE UNIT

The hydraulic data used in the case study are provided in this supplementary material to clarify the source of the operating ranges and engineering constraints adopted in the simulations. The data are based on the D1409BGV03 hydraulic model of a variable-speed pumped-storage unit and include the operating envelopes in pumping and generating modes, short-time operating boundaries, head-dependent operating data, no-load speed and guide-vane opening data, and complete characteristic curves. These data are used to define the nominal operating region, constraint limits, and representative operating points in the control simulations. The proposed control method itself is not restricted to this specific hydraulic model.

Fig. 1 Pumping-mode operating envelope in the input-power-head plane

Fig. 2 Pumping-mode operating envelope in the flow-rate-head plane

Fig. 3 Turbine-mode characteristic curves and admissible operating envelope

Fig. 4 Expected short-time operating envelope in pumping mode considering speed, head, maximum input power, hump margin, and cavitation constraints

Fig. 5 Expected short-time operating envelope in pumping mode considering speed, head, maximum input power, hump margin, and cavitation constraints.

Fig. 6 Complete characteristic curves in the N11-Q11 plane

Fig. 7 Complete characteristic curves in the N11-Q11 plane